

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2025, № 2 (Май)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

Научный журнал по научной и инновационной терапии
основано в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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ISSN
2181-418X

2025, № 2 (Май)

Адрес редакции:

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28.05.2022 г.

Подписано в печать 20.04.2025.

Формат 60×84 1/8

Усл. П.л. 41,39

Заказ 104

Тираж 50 экз.

Отпечатано в типографии Шарк

140151, г. Бухары,

ул. Амира Темура, 18

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PRELIMINARY RESULTS: ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AND ORTHOSTATIC HYPOTENSION IN SUPERCENTENARIANS

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Resume

The study's goal is to determine the prevalence of arterial hypertension (AH) and orthostatic hypotension (OH) in supercentenarians (those 95 years of age and older) as well as its effects on mortality. Materials and techniques A multidisciplinary team consisting of a geriatrician, nurse, and social worker conducted a thorough geriatric assessment at home for 82 supercentenarians that were 95 years of age or older (minimum age: 95, maximum age: 105). The duration of the prospective observation was three years (36 months).

Results: 78% had a history of hypertension. In the supine position, the mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) was 74 ± 12.8 mmHg (44 to 197 mmHg), and the mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) was 151 ± 27.9 mmHg (100 to 216 mmHg). Of the 61 centenarians who underwent the orthostatic test, 31% had OH. A higher intake of antihypertensive medications was not linked to the prevalence of OH. Within three years, forty-four study participants passed away. Mortality was unaffected by blood pressure (BP), a history of hypertension, or the presence of OH ($p > 0.05$). Conclusions: Hypertension and OH are quite prevalent in supercentenarians, and their SBP and DBP fluctuate widely. Mortality over three years was unaffected by blood pressure, hypertension, or OH. Additional studies are needed to better understand the health status of centenarians and the factors affecting the prognosis.

Keywords: geriatrics, long-livers, orthostatic hypotension, arterial hypertension.

DASTLABKI NATIJALAR: UZOQ YASHOVCHI INSONLARDA ARTERIAL GIPERTENZIYA VA ORTOSTATIK GIPOTENZIYA

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Rezyume.

Tadqiqot maqsadi— supercentenarianlarda (95 yosh va undan katta) arterial gipertenziya (AH) va ortostatik gipotenziya (OH) tarqalishi va o'limga ta'sirini baholash.

Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqot ishtirokchilari 95 yosh va undan katta yoshdagi 82 nafar supercentenarianlarni (minimal yoshi 95 yosh, maksimal 105 yosh) o'z ichiga olgan, ular uyda multidisipliner jamoa (geriatr, hamshira va ijtimoiy ishchi) tomonidan keng qamrovli geriatric baholashdan o'tgan. Istiqbolli kuzatish 3 yil (36 oy) davom etdi.

Natijalar: Gipertenziya tarixi 78% da qayd etilgan. Yotgan holatda o'rtacha sistolik qon bosimi (SBP) $151 \pm 27,9$ mmHg edi. Art. (100 dan 216 mm Hg gacha) va diastolik qon bosimi (DBP) $74 \pm 12,8$ mm Hg. Art. (44 dan 197 mm Hg gacha). Ortostatik testni o'tkazgan 61 yuz yillikning 31 foizida OH aniqlangan. OH mavjudligi antihipertenziv dorilarni ko'proq qabul qilish bilan bog'liq emas. 3 yil davomida 44 tadqiqot ishtirokchisi vafot etdi. Qon bosimi (BP) darajasi, gipertenziya tarixi va OH mavjudligi o'linga ta'sir qilmadi ($p > 0,05$). Xulosa: Supercentenarianlar SBP va DBP ning keng doirasiga ega va gipertenziya va OH yuqori tarqalishiga ega. Qon bosimi darajasi, gipertenziya va OH mavjudligi 3 yil davomida o'linga ta'sir qilmadi. Yuz yillikning salomatlik holatini va prognozga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni yaxshiroq tushunish uchun ko'proq tadqiqotlar talab etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: keksalar, uzoq jigarlar, ortostatik gipotenziya, arterial gipertenziya.

ПРЕДВАРИТЕЛЬНЫЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИИ И ОРТОСТАТИЧЕСКОЙ ГИПОТОНИИ У СУПЕРДОЛГОЖИТЕЛЕЙ

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Резюме.

Цель исследования — оценить распространенность и влияние на смертность артериальной гипертензии (АГ) и ортостатической гипотонии (ОГ) у супердолгожителей (95 лет и старше).

Материалы и методы. Участниками исследования стали 82 супердолгожителя в возрасте от 95 лет и старше (минимальный возраст 95 лет, максимальный — 105 лет), которым на дому была выполнена комплексная гериатрическая оценка мультидисциплинарной командой (врач-гериатр, медицинская сестра и социальный работник). Проспективное наблюдение составило 3 года (36 месяцев).

Результаты: Анамнез АГ отмечен у 78%. Среднее систолическое артериальное давление (САД) в положении лежа составило $151 \pm 27,9$ мм рт. ст. (от 100 до 216 мм рт. ст.), а диастолическое артериальное давление (ДАД) $74 \pm 12,8$ мм рт. ст. (от 44 до 197 мм рт. ст.). ОГ выявлена у 31% из 61 долгожителя, выполнившего ортостатическую пробу. Наличие ОГ не было ассоциировано с большим приемом антигипертензивных препаратов. В течение 3 лет умерли 44 участника исследования. Уровень артериального давления (АД), анамнез АГ и наличие ОГ не влияли на смертность ($p > 0,05$). Выводы: У супердолгожителей выявляются широкий диапазон САД и ДАД, высокая распространенность АГ и ОГ. Уровень АД, наличие АГ и ОГ не влияли на смертность в течение 3 лет. Необходимо проведение дополнительных исследований для лучшего понимания состояния здоровья долгожителей и факторов, влияющих на прогноз.

Ключевые слова: гериатрия, долгожители, ортостатическая гипотония, артериальная гипертензия.

Prevalence and coincidence of hypertension and orthostatic hypotension in preand centenarians and their effect on mortality: preliminary results

Abstract

Objective. to calculate the prevalence of orthostatic hypotension (OH) and arterial hypertension (HTN) in centenarians (those 95 years of age and older) and its effects on mortality. **Methods and design.** Eighty-two super-long-livers (minimum age of 95, maximum age of 105) participated in the study. A multidisciplinary team consisting of a geriatrician, nurse, and social worker conducted a thorough geriatric examination at their homes. For three years (36 months), the subsequent prospective observation was conducted.

Results.

78% of patients had a history of HTN. In the supine position, the mean diastolic blood pressure (DBP) was 74 ± 12.8 mm Hg (44–197 mm Hg), and the mean systolic blood pressure (SBP) was 151 ± 27.9 mm Hg (100–216 mm Hg). Of the 61 long-livers that were able to complete an orthostatic test, 31% had OH. Higher antihypertensive medication intake was not linked to the prevalence of OH. Forty-four study participants passed away within three years. Mortality was unaffected by blood pressure (BP), history of hypertension, or presence of OH ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusions. Centenarians have a significant prevalence of OH and HTN, as well as a wide range of SBP and DBP. Over a three-year period, mortality was unaffected by blood pressure, the prevalence of HTN, or OH. To have a better understanding of the health status of long-lived individuals and the factors influencing their prognosis, more research is required.

Key words:geriatrics, centenarians, orthostatic hypotension, hypertension

Introduction

One of the most prevalent conditions that shortens life expectancy and degrades quality of life is arterial hypertension (AH). From 600 million in 1980 to 1 billion in 2008, its prevalence has grown globally, and this growth is linked to both an increase in the total population and an increase in life expectancy [1]. As people age, the occurrence of AH rises. A meta-analysis of national databases in the United States (2007–2009), Canada (2007–2010), and the United Kingdom (2006) found that the prevalence of AH in the elderly (age group 60–80 years) is, on average, twice as high as in middle-aged individuals (age group 40–59 years). It varies between 18.4 and 31.1% in middle-aged individuals and between 53.2 and 63.7% in older patients [2]. AH, or arterial hypertension, is a prevalent condition that lowers life expectancy and degrades quality of life. Because of both an increase in life expectancy and a rise in the global population, its prevalence has risen from 600 million in 1980 to 1 billion in 2008 [1]. As people age, AH becomes more common. The prevalence of AH in the elderly (age group 60 to 80 years) is, on average, twice as high as in middle-aged people (age group 40 to 59 years), with variations ranging from 53.2 to 63.7% in older patients and from 18.4 to 31.1% in middle-aged people, following a meta-

analysis of national databases in the UK (2006), Canada (2007–2010), and the United States (2007–2009) [2]. Hypertension is frequently linked to OH [6]. Patients in the long-liver group (95 years and older) were not included in the majority of investigations on hypertension and OH.

The aim of our research The objective was to determine the prevalence of OH and hypertension in people 95 years of age and older who were nearing or had reached the 100-year milestone, as well as the effect these conditions had on survival during the course of a 3-year prospective observation.

Materials and methods

The centenarian or his or her guardian may sign an informed permission form for the examination. A designated social worker accompanied the centenarian on the home visit. Eighty-two centenarians (mean age of 98 years, minimum age of 95 years, maximum age of 105 years, standard deviation (SD) 1.9, with 87.8% of them being female) participated in the study (Table 1). A mobile geriatric team consisting of a geriatrician, nurse, and social worker assessed research participants at home while they were accompanied by family members, guardians, and/or caretakers. The doctor performed a physical examination during the visit, which included taking the patient's heart rate and blood pressure. A mechanical tonometer that passed the metrological test in compliance with the current rules was used to do the measurement using the auscultatory method. The measurement was taken while sitting or in the supine position (for research participants who did not get out of bed and had very little physical activity) and then one or three minutes after getting out of bed. Three minutes after standing up, the OH criterion was a drop in systolic blood pressure (SBP) of 20 mmHg or more, and/or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of 10 mmHg or more [7]. Using the medical data that were available, the history of hypertension was elucidated. Interviews with the centenarian, family members, caretakers, and social workers who assist with medicine purchases were used to gather information on current medication use. After three years, information on life status was gathered by calling centenarians, family members, or caretakers, or by contacting the relevant social service institution. For statistical analysis, GraphPad Prism Version 8.1.1 (224) was used. The findings are shown as mean values ($M \pm SD$, \pm standard deviation). χ^2 (Ch-square) was used to compare qualitative values. The Kaplan-Meier survival curve analysis was used to evaluate survival. At $p < 0.05$, differences were deemed statistically significant.

Results

prevalence of high blood pressure. 64 out of 82 study participants (78%), had a history of hypertension. 53 (72.8%) of those surveyed were taking antihypertensive medication at the time of the examination. Eight individuals (14%), whereas 27 individuals (42.2%) were taking just one medication, were receiving multicomponent antihypertensive therapy (three or more medicines). The most frequently used drugs were beta-blockers and angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, with corresponding frequencies of use of 35.9% and 32.8%. Elderly individuals were less

likely to take medications from other classes, such as diuretics (20%) and calcium channel blockers (23%). None of the trial participants were treated with alpha-blockers or centrally acting medications. SBP was 151.4 ± 27.9 mm Hg on average. Table 2 shows that SBP was 74 ± 12 mmHg and DBP was 74 ± 12 mmHg. Thirty percent of study participants had an SBP of less than 140 mmHg at the time of evaluation, while 17.8% had an SBP of more than 180 mmHg (Fig. 1, 2). 61 centenarians underwent an orthostatic test; seven were unable to stand up straight, and fourteen refused. Average SBP and DBP drops were 8.5 ± 17.3 mmHg (highest drop of 50 mmHg) and -0.7 ± 11.5 mmHg (maximum drop of 36 mmHg). OH was present in 19 (31.1%) centenarians. There were no differences in the prevalence of OH between those with and without hypertension: 4 (23.5%) centenarians without hypertension and 15 (34.1%) with hypertension had OH ($p > 0.54$). There was no significant difference in the number of antihypertensive medications taken by centenarians with and without OH: 1.6 ± 1.1 versus 1.1 ± 1.1 ($p = 0.08$). Vital status information for 69 participants was collected after three years; 25 (36.2%) centenarians were still living, and 44 (63.8%) had passed away. At the first assessment, the SBP and DBP of survivors were 156.8 ± 24.7 and 78.61 ± 13.4 mmHg, respectively. As a result, 72% had hypertension and 31.6% had OH; 84.1% of those who passed away had hypertension and 32.3% had OH; the initial examination's SBP and DBP were 145.9 ± 25.2 and 72.2 ± 13.9 mm Hg, respectively. There was no correlation between death and the levels of SBP and DBP, hypertension, or OH, according to Kaplan-Meier survival analysis (Fig. 3).

Discussion: The number of persons who are 90–100 years old is steadily increasing each year. Over 50% of those born in 2000 will be able to enjoy their 100th birthday, while 15% of women and 12% of males born in 1950 will live to be 90 years old, according to international publications [8]. The improvement in medical care quality is the main factor contributing to the increase in life expectancy. However, it is well known that among individuals who live to such a high age, age-related disorders either do not arise at all or appear much later in life [11]. "Negligible aging" is another term for this phenomenon [10]. Traditional risk factors, such as hyperlipidemia and hyperglycemia, may not have an impact on life prognosis in very elderly patients, or their relationship to them may be inverse when compared to younger individuals (for instance, high total cholesterol is linked to lower mortality in individuals aged 85 and older) [12, 13]. A J-shaped relationship has been described for BP and the risk of death in elderly patients; studies conducted in the USA (war veterans over 80 years old) and Europe (INVEST) demonstrated that in groups with SBP above 139 mm Hg and DBP above 89 mm Hg, survival was higher than in groups with more stringent BP control [14, 15]. In our study, a history of hypertension did not affect 3-year survival. We also did not find an effect of OH on survival, unlike the Honolulu Heart Program study, which noted an increase in mortality in men aged 71 to 93 years with OH [5]. The differences in the results can be explained by the older age of the patients included in our study, as well as a

relatively small proportion of men in our sample (n = 10, 12.2%). Supercentenarians were not included in most multicenter studies devoted to the determination of modifiable risk factors affecting survival. At present, it is known that hypertension and OH are widespread in this age group. Foreign studies have demonstrated that some of the known risk factors cannot be used for this age group [12, 13]. Due to the resulting complexity of using standard prognostic factors and the uniqueness of the 100-year-old cohort, people need to continue research into creating algorithms for a personalized approach.

Conclusion

Hypertension and OH are quite prevalent in supercentenarians, and their SBP and DBP fluctuate widely. Our research indicates that over a three-year period, mortality in the supercentenarian group is unaffected by blood pressure, hypertension, or OH. To learn more about the health status of centenarians and the variables influencing their prognosis, more research is required.

References

1. World Health Organization (WHO). Global Health Observatory (GHO) data. Raised blood pressure. [Electronic resource]. URL: https://www.who.int/gho/ncd/risk_factors/blood_pressure_prevalence_text/en/
2. Joffres M, Falaschetti E, Gillespie C, Robitaille C, Loustalot F, Poulter N et al. Hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment and control in national surveys from England, the USA and Canada, and correlation with stroke and ischemic heart disease mortality: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2013;3(8):e003423. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2013-003423
3. Saedon NI, Tan MP, Frith J. The prevalence of orthostatic hypotension: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci*. 2020;75(1):117–122. doi:10.1093/gerona/gly188
4. Aronow WS, Fleg JL, Pepine CJ, Artinian NT, Bakris G, Brown AS et al. ACCF Task Force. ACCF/AHA 2011 expert consensus document on hypertension in the elderly: a report of the American College of Cardiology Foundation Task Force on Clinical Expert Consensus Documents. *Circulation*. 2011;123(21):2434–2506. doi:10.1161/CIR.0b013e31821daaf6. Epub 2011 Apr 25.
5. Masaki KH, Schatz IJ, Burchfiel CM, Sharp DS, Chiu D, Foley D et al. Orthostatic hypotension predicts mortality in elderly men: the Honolulu Heart Program. *Circulation*. 1998;98(21):2290–2295.
6. Di Stefano C, Milazzo V, Totaro S, Sobrero G, Ravera A, Milan A et al. Orthostatic hypotension in a cohort of hypertensive patients referring to a hypertension clinic. *J Hum Hypertens*. 2015;29(10):599–603. doi:10.1038/jhh.2014.130
7. Ostroumova OD, Cherniaeva MS, Petrova MM, Golovina OV. Orthostatic hypotension: definition, pathophysiology, classification, prognostic aspects, diagnostics and treatment. *Rational Pharmacotherapy in Cardiology*. 2018;14(5):747–

756. doi.org/10.20996/1819-6446-2018-14-5-747-756. doi.org/10.20996/1819-6446-2018-14-5-747-756. In Russian].
8. Christensen K, Doblhammer G, Rau R, Vaupel JW. Ageing populations: the challenges ahead. *Lancet*. 2009;374(9696):1196–1208. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(09)61460-4
9. Crimmins EM. Lifespan and healthspan: past, present, and promise. *Gerontologist*. 2015;55(6):901–911. doi:10.1093/geront/gnv130
10. Franceschi C, Passarino G, Mari D, Monti D. Centenarians as a 21st century healthy aging model: A legacy of humanity and the need for a world-wide consortium (WWC100+). *Mech Ageing Dev*. 2017;165(PtB):55–58. doi:10.1016/j.mad.2017.06.002.
11. Evert J, Lawler E, Bogan H, Perls T. Morbidity profiles of centenarians: survivors, delayers, and escapers. *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci*. 2003;58(3):232–237.
12. Schatz IJ, Masaki K, Yano K, Chen R, Rodriguez BL, Curb JD. Cholesterol and all-cause mortality in elderly people from the Honolulu Heart Program: a cohort study. *Lancet*. 2001;358(9279):351–355.
13. Schupf N, Costa R, Luchsinger J, Tang MX, Lee JH, Mayeux R. Relationship between plasma lipids and all-cause mortality in nondemented elderly. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 2005;53(2):219–226.
14. Oates DJ, Berlowitz DR, Glickman ME, Silliman RA, Borzecki AM. Blood pressure and survival in the oldest old. *J Am Geriatr Soc*. 2007;55(3):383–388. doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2007.01069.x
15. Denardo SJ, Gong Y, Nichols WW, Messerli FH, Bavry AA, Cooper-Dehoff RM et al. Blood pressure and outcomes in very old hypertensive coronary artery disease patients: an INVEST Substudy. *Am J Med*. 2010;123(8):719–726. doi:10.1016/j.amjmed.2010.02.014
16. Saidova, L.B., Saidova, M.K., Mirzaeva, D.B., Kuvvatov, Z.K., & Ashurova, N.G. (2019, July). Optimization of medical care for patients with acute poisoning at the prehospital stage by emergency medical care team. In Of XY international Research and practice conference England, London (pp. 120-122).
17. Saidova, L.B., Saidova, M.K., Shodiev, A.S., Kuvvatov, Z.K., & Ashurova, N.G. (2019). Improving the quality of rendering assistance with acute poisons of sychopharmacological preparations according to the Bukhara center of emergency medical assistance in the toxicology division of XY international Research and practice conference England. PROSPECTS OF WORLD SCIENCE-2019, 127.
18. Saidova, L.B., Saidova, M.K., Kuvvatov, Z.Kh., and Abdullaeva, N.Z. (2019, June). Real-life practice: Glycoside poisoning – diagnostic and treatment challenges. In: 4th eduindex international multidisciplinary conference, Zurich, Switzerland (pp. 37-38).

19. Saidova, L. B., & Shodieva, N. U. (2021). Frequency of risk factors for overweight and obesity in young adults-review lecture. *Biology and Integrative Medicine*, (1 (48)), 194-206.
20. Saidova, L. B., & Shodieva, N. U. (2021). Prevalence of Risk Factors for Overweight and Obesity in Young Adults During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Primary Health Care. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 137-141.
21. Saidova, L.B., Saidova, M.K., Kuvvatov, Z.Kh., and Abdullaeva, N.Z. (2019). Real-life practice: Glycoside poisoning – diagnostic and treatment challenges. 4th International Multidisciplinary Conference eduindex, Zurich, Switzerland.
22. Saidova, L. B., Karimov, U. A., & Saidova, M. K. (2009). Morbidity of preschool children attending and not attending preschool institutions. *Issues of Practical Pediatrics*, 4(2), 90-93.
23. Saidova, L. B., & Nazarova, A. B. (2022). Prevention of infertility in women of reproductive age with obesity and vitamin D deficiency.
24. Saidova, L. B. (2020). Improving the quality of life of patients with chronic glomerulonephritis using statins. *Biology and Integrative Medicine*, (2 (42)), 14-23.
25. L. B, S., & M. Sh., J. . (2023). Clinical and Prognostic Aspects of the Course of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in Patients Who Survived Covid-19. *Journal of Injury and Disability Research*, 2(7), 75–78.